

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

An IOC Newsletter on toxic algae and algal blooms

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/news.htm>

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Phytoplankton blooms in the North Atlantic: results from the Continuous Plankton Recorder survey 2001/2002

The Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) survey was instigated by Alister Hardy in 1931 and has since evolved over a period of seven decades into a unique marine monitoring programme. The survey contains biological information on over 450 taxa of phytoplankton and zooplankton and provides the scientific community with its only measure of the state of oceanic plankton over oceanic space and decadal time scales. The self-contained automatic plankton recorders are towed at monthly intervals by ships-of-opportunity along a number of transects that continuously collect plankton from a standard depth of 7 m. Using this simple but highly

cost effective technique, CPRs have been towed by volunteer ships for over 4 million nautical miles, resulting in the collection of nearly 200,000 plankton samples from all over the North Atlantic. On certain standard routes there now exists a virtually unbroken monthly coverage going back to 1948. In this brief article we highlight some of the CPR surveys phytoplankton results recorded in the North Atlantic for the year 2001/2002. In the case of the CPR survey, the term 'unusual' or 'large' in reference to phytoplankton blooms refers to a population increases greater than four standard deviations above the species recorded baseline mean (baseli-

ne mean: 1980-2000). Notable blooms that are geographically large refer to patch sizes greater than 100 km in diameter. The majority of data analysis has been performed to highlight the year 2001 in context to the long-term dataset. 2002 sample data is presented here as preliminary and has not yet undergone quality checks.

The spring bloom in the North Atlantic 2001

In early February 2001 in the North Sea a couple of early diatom blooms occurred including *Odontella regia* and *Thalassionema nitzschioides*. A very
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• Japan

The «Red Tide Watcher» Project

Eutrophication of the coastal waters in Asia has been accelerated by rapid economic growth, leading to increased frequency and intensity of red tide occurrences in the region. This demands an efficient monitoring of red tides to minimize their negative impacts on fisheries resources, marine ecosystems and human health. Considering the application of satellite remote sensing techniques to monitor red tides that spread widely in a short time, the «Red Tide Watcher» project sponsored by the Japanese Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) was initiated in October 2002. This project aims at

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Participants of the first workshop on red tide monitoring in the Asian coastal waters.

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early bloom of *Thalassionema nitzschioides* developed in the second week of February on Georges Bank (north-west Atlantic) which was also present the following month. *Rhizosolenia imbrica shrubsolei*, *Thalassiosira* spp. and *Thalassionema nitzschioides* dominated early March and April blooms in the North Sea. Peak spring biomass reached a maximum in the third week of March in the North Sea, one week earlier than the baseline mean (1948-2000). Early April saw the development of a large bloom of *Thalassiosira* spp. off the Celtic Sea shelf edge and in the Bay of Biscay. The dominating species in the shelf areas of the north-west Atlantic (Georges Bank, Scotian Shelf and the Grand Banks) around this time were *Rhizosolenia hebetata semispina* and *Chaetoceros* spp. The northern shelf edge of the Grand Banks continued to experience very large blooms of *Chaetoceros* spp. well into June.

Overall phytoplankton biomass 1948-2001

Figure 1 shows the long-term monthly values of phytoplankton colour (an index of total phytoplankton biomass) in the central North Sea from 1948 to 2001. It is obvious from the figure that there has been a large increase in phytoplankton biomass since the late 1980s. From the late 1940s to the late 1980s, the majority of biomass was restricted to the spring and autumn bloom periods, i.e. diatoms dominated the phytoplankton assemblage. Since the late 1980s, biomass has increased throughout the seasonal cycle. While spring and autumnal blooms values have remained relatively the same compared to the baseline mean (1948-2000), phytoplankton colour has significantly increased during the winter and in particular the summer months. This suggests that the phytoplankton community has shifted from a traditional dominance of diatoms to flagellates and dinoflagellates. 2001 continued with this trend with particularly high values recorded in July. In other parts of the North Atlantic, high increases in phytoplankton biomass are also seen off the Newfoundland Shelf (with an increase in winter blooms), the Scotian Shelf and the Labrador Sea. In

the northern North Atlantic and in the sub-polar gyre, phytoplankton biomass has been declining over the last decade. Taking the North Atlantic as a whole, the large-scale spatial patterns over time show similarities to satellite derived estimates of chlorophyll over the same time-period.

Exceptional and Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs)

As well as providing an index of phytoplankton biomass (phytoplankton colour), the CPR survey identifies approximately 170 phytoplankton taxa. Figure 2 shows the occurrence of exceptional phytoplankton blooms in the North Atlantic and the North Sea in 2001 (the majority of diatom species have been removed, see spring bloom text). Apart from diatom species, by far the most common bloom forming taxa recorded by the CPR survey in 2001 was Coccolithaceae in particular the species *Coccolithus pelagicus*. In early

June the CPR survey recorded a massive bloom of Coccolithaceae between Scotland and Iceland approximately 600 km in diameter. Large blooms of Coccolithaceae were also recorded in the northern North Sea and at the entrance of the English Channel in July. An exceptionally large bloom of *Ceratium longipes* occurred off the Scotian Shelf in early July (~ 400 km). Apart from geographically extensive blooms, of particular note are the occurrences of Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) in the North Sea. Large blooms of *Dinophysis* spp. occurred off north-east Scotland in July and August and off the northern Danish coast also in July. Although not considered toxic, large blooms of *Ceratium furca*, such as those recorded in the northern North Sea in July and August, can lead to hypoxia which have been known to have a detrimental effect on benthic fauna. The red-tide forming species *Noctiluca scintillans* occurred in July off the Dutch coast and in August

Fig. 1 (top) Typical early development of the spring bloom in the north-east Atlantic, beginning on Dogger Bank, the Southern Bight and at the entrance to the Skagerrak in March and spreading to other shelf areas in April; (bottom) long-term monthly values of phytoplankton colour in the central North Sea from 1948 to 2001. Circles denote colour values > 2 SD above the long-term monthly mean.

Fig. 2. Exceptional and offshore HABs recorded by the CPR survey in the North Atlantic (conical projection) and North Sea in 2001. Exceptional blooms include Coccolithaceae and all dinoflagellates and species associated with Harmful Algal Blooms (all diatom species except *Cylindrotheca closterium*, *Leptocylindrus danicus* and *Thalassiothrix longissima* have been excluded). 'Exceptional blooms' are species that have occurred 4 standard deviations above the species recorded sample mean (baseline mean 1980-2000).

1: Coccolithaceae, 2: *Ceratium furca*, 3: *Dinophysis* spp., 4: *Noctiluca scintillans*, 5: *Ceratium macroceros*, 6: *Ceratium fusus*, 7: *Cylindrotheca closterium*, 8: *Thalassiothrix longissima*, 9: *Ceratium longipes*, 10: *Exuviaella* spp., 11: *Leptocylindrus danicus*, 12: *Gonyaulax* spp.

in the Southern Bight. Of other note was the occurrence of *Cylindrotheca closterium* recorded in June at the southern entrance to the Irish Sea. This diatom species has been associated with the production of foam and mucilage. Preliminary evidence for 2002 suggests that there have been extensive blooms in the Labrador Sea of *Ceratium aciticum*, *Detonula* spp. and *Navicula planamembranacea*. Large blooms of *Thalassiothrix longissima* have also been recorded in the central North Sea in early spring 2002. The presence of this species in such large numbers is associated with large influxes of Atlantic water and hence nutrients into the North Sea. Future work using the CPR survey results will include an investigation into whether phytoplankton blooms are increasing over the last few decades in the North Atlantic and in particular around suspected coastal eutrophicated regions

and whether phytoplankton blooms are predominately driven by climatic or anthropogenic changes.

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CALL FOR RESEARCH

GEOHAB invites research consortia and individual researchers to submit outlines of their proposals or already funded projects for GEOHAB endorsement.

GEOHAB will only be successful when a critical mass of research is networked and thereby can benefit from interaction and common framework activities.

GEOHAB in particular invites research on HAB in upwelling systems, and fjords and coastal embayments at the present time.

See all details on participation in GEOHAB at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/GEOHAB.htm>

? Taxonomy problems ?

The IOC Taxonomic Reference List of Toxic Microalgae is regularly updated and is now presented in a new attractive format.

The list is intended as an authoritative reference that reflects current use of names and synonyms.

The Editors are Ø. Moestrup, (Chair), G.A. Codd, M. Elbrächter, M.A. Faust, S. Fraga, Y. Fukuyo, G. Cronberg, Y. Halim, F.J.R. Taylor and A. Zingone.

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/data.htm>

CODEX revision

The CODEX ALIMENTARIUS Committee for Fish and Fisheries Products has recommended that an expert review be made with the view to revise the CODEX Code of Practice for Marine Biotoxins. An WHO-IOC-FAO Expert Consultation has been set up to address this and a first workshop was held at the Food Authority of Ireland, 22-24 March. The final expert consultation will be held in Oslo, Norway, in September. This work has merged with the IPHAB Task Team on Biotoxins and is chaired by the IPHAB Vice Chair, Dr. Phil Busby, New Zealand. More information at <http://www.who.int/foodsafety/en/> under 'Upcoming Events'.

• Italy

Microcystin concentrations in water and ichthyofauna of Massaciuccoli Wetlands (Tuscany)

Summary/Abstract

The present report deals with the analysis of the water and the ichthyofauna of the Massaciuccoli wetland (Tuscany, Italy), where blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa* have been observed since about ten years ago. A monitoring study based on monthly collections of water samples was carried out from June to November 2003 and the results show microcystin levels greater than $160 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ in superficial waters. Microcystin reaches the highest levels in the liver of *Mugil cephalus* ($10,900 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) and in the "head" of the allochthonous crustacean *Procambarus clarkii* ($1,092 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). When compared with the control group, an increase of the concentration of the toxin was detected in the liver of *Carassius auratus* experimentally reared for one month in lake water collected during blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa*.

Introduction

Massaciuccoli Lake, which originated from the sea, lies within a large wetland, partly reclaimed, situated near the coast between Torre del Lago and Viareggio (Lucca); the lake covers an area of approximately 700 ha, has an average depth of 1.6 m, a maximum depth of 2.5 m and an average volume of about 11,000,000 m³.

The lake is connected to the sea by its only effluent, the Burlamacca channel, situated on the northwest side of the wetland. The waters of the Massaciuccoli ecosystem are brackish, with the highest concentrations of chlorides - about $4,000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ - near the hydraulic doors, located at the end of the Burlamacca channel; the lowest concentrations of Cl⁻ (600 to $1,000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) can be found within the lake basin. The lake has no affluents: mainly water is pumped into the lake by the water-scooping machines of reclamation works, located for the most part on the southern side of the lake. Human pressure on this ecosystem consists mainly of emissions from sewage purification plants of

the neighboring villages, and of water draining from intensive agriculture, and has caused a rapid increase in eutrophication in the last 50 years. In 2003 the average concentration of chlorophyll *a* was $48.19 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, with the highest level of $184.3 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; lake clarity, measured by Secchi disk transparency, was 0.43 m, with a minimum of 0.15 m; the euphotic zone depth (Zeu 5%) was 0.85 m, and the average concentration of Cyanophyceae was 825,000 cells mL⁻¹, which corresponds to 94% of the total number of cells [1].

Since 1972, endemic blooms of the microalga *Prymnesium parvum* have occurred in Massaciuccoli Lake, causing large periodic fishes mortalities [2,3]. Increasingly large blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa* have been observed in the last ten years, and often lead to the formation of dense scums. The blooms of *Prymnesium parvum* occur in wintertime and in early spring, while the blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa* take place in summer and autumn. The regular alternation of the blooms of the two species shows a reciprocal allelopathic effect induced by each other toxins.

In this framework, we performed the present research to: 1) monitor the concentrations of *M. aeruginosa* and microcystin in the waters of the Massaciuccoli ecosystem; 2) study the intake and the accumulation of toxins in body tissues of the ichthyofauna; 3) identify the fish species and tissues where the toxin reaches highest concentrations. This study should be regarded as well as an attempt to assess the potential threat to public health posed by the ingestion of fishes or crustaceans contaminated by algal toxins: according to the World Health Organization [4], the TDI (tolerable daily intake) of microcystin LR (the most toxic for humans), in relation to hepatic pathologies, is $0.04 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of body weight. Therefore a 70 kg adult should not exceed a daily dose of 2.8 μg of microcystin.

Material and methods

Water samples (3 liters) were collected monthly from June to November 2003 with a set of three one-meter-long PVC pipe cores, dipped perpendicular to the surface, which could be closed at one end.

M. aeruginosa counts were performed in 1 or 2 mL of water with an inverted microscope at 100X and 600X.

Microcystin concentrations in water were determined with the ELISA immunological procedure; in fishes and in *Procambarus* the tests were conducted on water extracts (1:10) of the flesh, of the liver [5], or of the whole body (small Caspian sand smelts - *Atherina mocon* - and crustaceans).

Results

The results of tests conducted on fish (liver, flesh, eggs) and crustacean samples are shown in Table 1, which shows the average, lowest, and highest concentrations of microcystin ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) in 44 samples of flesh, liver and bowels, two samples of eggs, three of whole Caspian-sand smelts, four of *Procambarus clarkii* (head and tail), and one whole specimen of *P. clarkii*; Table 1 also reports the amounts that can be safely ingested by a 70 kg adult.

Flesh and liver from *Mugil cephalus* from the Northern Ligurian Sea were analyzed as a control (Table 2), and shown to have extremely low levels of microcystins, probably due to specific links between the g-globulins on the surface of the wells of the test kit and the liver extracts from the fish; an alternative reason may be that *Mugil cephalus* sometimes feeds in estuaries where occasional blooms of Cyanophyceae occur.

As a further control, two specimens of *Carassius auratus*, bought in an aquarium shop, were kept respectively: one in the water of a part of Massaciuccoli wetland called San Rocchino, at a time when there was a consistent scum of *M. aeruginosa*, and the other in tap water. After one month, the concentration of microcystin in the liver of the specimen

Table 1

Species and tissues	Nr. of specimens examined	Microcystin average concentration	Microcystin highest concentration and sampling area	Microcystin lowest concentration	Kg of fish corresponding to 1 TDI for a 70 kg human*
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i> (Lac.) (flesh)	5	1.86	2.7 (Cava Sisa)	1	1.03
<i>Micropterus salmoides</i> (liver)	5	3.42	5.4 (Cava Sisa)	1.2	0.52
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (L.) (flesh)	8	1.7	1.57 (Fosso Morto)	1	1.7
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (liver)	8	1.62	3.1 (Fosso Morto)	1	0.90
<i>Cyprinus carpio</i> (eggs)	1	1.4	1.4 (Fosso Morto)	1.4	2
<i>Mugil cephalus</i> (L.) (flesh)	10	2.10	5.09 (P. Grande)	1	0.47
<i>Mugil cephalus</i> (liver)	10	5,296	10,900 (P. Grande)	634	0.26 g
<i>Mugil cephalus</i> (eggs)	1		8.5 (P. Grande)		330 g
<i>Iactulurus</i> sp. (flesh)	4	1.23	1.6 (Piaggetta)	1	1.75
<i>Iactulurus</i> sp. (liver)	4	2.67	4 (Piaggetta)	2.1	0.7
<i>Scardinius</i> sp. (flesh)	3	1.40	1.77 (Incrociata)	1.1	1.6
<i>Scardinius</i> sp. (liver)	3	3.70	5.3 (Incrociata)	1.95	0.53
<i>Carassius</i> sp. (flesh)	10	1.24	1.3 (P. Grande)	1	2.6
<i>Carassius</i> sp. (liver)	10	3.23	8.1 (P. Grande)	1	0.35
<i>Atherina</i> sp. (whole)	three 30g specimen	4.2	2.35 (Lake)	1	1.12
<i>Procambarus clarkii</i> (tail)	4	1.43	1.64 (Canale "Le 15")	1	1.70
<i>Procambarus clarkii</i> (head)	4	21886	1092 (Canale "Le 15")	16	2.56 g
<i>Procambarus clarkii</i> (whole)	1	120	120 (Canale "Le 15")	120	23 g
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i> (L.) (flesh)	2	1.16	1.54 (Canale "Le 15")	1	1.8
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i> (L.) (liver)	2	12.7	16 (Canale "Le 15")	10	0.17
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (L.) (flesh)	1	1.47	1.47 (San Rocchino)	1.47	1.9
<i>Anguilla ang.</i> (L.) (bowels)	1	1.6	1.6 (San Rocchino)	1.6	1.75

* The TDI is expressed in kg unless otherwise specified

reared in San Rocchino water was 16 times higher than the concentration in the specimen reared in tap water.

Discussion

The results of this investigation of water samples and ichthyofauna of Massaciuccoli Lake show first of all that blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa* occur

mainly in summer and autumn, either in dry or rainy periods. Besides, during the collection of samples we noticed that scums of *Microcystis aeruginosa* occur on the water surface most frequently on the north-west side of the lake, namely in the west stretch of the Burlamacca channel and in site indicated as San Rocchino. The highest concentrations

of *Microcystis* were detected in June and in November (Table 3), while the highest concentrations of microcystin were detected in August, September, and October (Table 4). During the presence of the scums, the concentration of *Microcystis* in superficial waters was very high (200,000 cell mL⁻¹), as well as the concentration of microcystin (> 160 µg L⁻¹). There are no indications that the blooms of *Microcystis aeruginosa* can cause death of fishes. Dead mallards and fishes were occasionally found during the presence of scums, but the causes of their death could not be established.

The highest microcystin concentrations were found in the liver of *Mugil cephalus* and in the head of *Procambarus clarkii*. The high toxin concentration in the flesh of the 10 *Mugil cephalus* of our sample (5.08 µg L⁻¹) show that a 70 kg adult should ingest 0.47 kg of fish in order to reach the TDI. Therefore, if the *Mugil cephalus* are accurately disemboweled the toxicological risk is relatively low. On the other hand, if the liver is ingested, the TDI is reached after eating 0.5 g of tissue containing the concentration of microcystin detected on average in our study (5,296 µg kg⁻¹), or eating only 0.26 g of tissue with the highest levels of microcystin (10,900 µg kg⁻¹). These results show that ingestion of only one fish liver affected by such high levels of microcystin may pose a serious hazard to humans. The ovaries from *Mugil cephalus* in which the highest concentrations of microcystin are present in their livers do not show particularly high levels of the toxin. In fact, the TDI is reached after the ingestion of 300 g of eggs at the concentrations detected in the present study.

Tests conducted on the head of *Procambarus*, where the bowels of the animal are located, confirm the potential hazard posed by this crustacean. The average concentration of

Table 2

Species and tissues	Nr. of specimens examined	Microcystin average concentration	Microcystin highest concentration and sampling area	Microcystin lowest concentration	Kg of fish corresponding to 1 TDI for a 70 kg human*
Sea <i>Mugil</i> (flesh)	3	1.35	1.7	1	1.64
Sea <i>Mugil</i> (liver)	3	2.20	2.4	2	1.27
<i>Carassius</i> without <i>Microcystis</i> (flesh)	1	1			2.8
<i>Carassius</i> without <i>Microcystis</i> (liver)	1	9.8			0.28
<i>Carassius</i> with <i>Microcystis</i> (flesh)	1	1			2.8
<i>Carassius</i> with <i>Microcystis</i> (liver)	1	159			17 g

* The TDI is expressed in kg unless otherwise specified

Table 3

Sampling area	Nov 02	Dec 02	Jan 03	Feb 03	Mar 03	Apr 03	May 03	Jun 03	Jul 03	Aug 03	Sep 03	Oct 03	Nov 03	High	Low	St. Dev.	
Middle of the lake	250	50	0	0	0	10	400	6,000	4,400	2,000	1,500	3,200	1,200	6,000	1,500	2,037	
Malfante	60		30	0	0	0	0	15,000	3,000	2,600		4,000	2,600	15,000	2,600	4,664	
Burlamacca	30		0	0	0	0	0	12,500	3,200	6,600	58,634	3,700	600	58,634	3,200	17,349	
S. Rocchino	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	12,000	3,400	1,000	1,520	3,400	1,500	12,000	1,000	3,470	
Incrociata	120		0	0	0	0	0	14,500	600	2,500		5,400	1,200	14,500	600	4,626	
Canale "Le 15"	95	0	2	30	0	10	50	12,000	1,000	1,200	2,010		0	800	12,000	0	3,412
Fosso Morto	0		0	80	0	0	0	13,000	0	2,600		14,500	800	14,500	0	5,725	
Centralino	120		0	0	0	0	0	10,000	0	1,400		4,200	15,000	10,000	0	3,247	
Barra					0		0		5,200								
Punta Grande						10											
S. Rocchino surface												200,000					
Highest values	250	50	30	80	0	10	400	15,000	5,200	6,600	58,634	14,500	15,000				
Rain (mm)	123.2	161.5	43.5	15.0	22.7	80.2	0.6	48.4	1.8	35.9	61.6	93.4					

Table 4

Sampling area	Nov 02	Dec 02	Jan 03	Feb 03	Mar 03	Apr 03	May 03	Jun 03	Jul 03	Aug 03	Sep 03	Oct 03	Nov 03	High	Low	St. Dev.
Middle of the lake	0.60	0.19	0.10	< 0.1	< 0.1	0.20	>1.6	1.42	1.02	< 1	3.31	2.90	<1	3.31	1.02	1.25
Malfante	0.70		< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1			4.81	1.67	1.44		5.60	1.1	5.60	0.70	2.20
Burlamacca	< 0.1		< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1		3.61	1.70	3.58	> 16	6.90	<1	6.90	1.70	2.16
San Rocchino	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1		3.94	< 0.1	< 1	12.45	>16	6.9	>16	3.94	6.02
Incrociata	< 0.1							4.11	< 0.1	1.22		2.00	<1	4.11	1.22	1.50
Canale "Le 15"	< 0.1	< 0.1					0.34	2.43	< 0.1	< 1	< 1		<1	2.43	0.34	1.48
Fosso Morto	< 0.1							3.71	< 0.1	> 16		5.00	<1	>216	3.71	0.91
Centralino	4.20				0.20			2.78	< 0.1	> 16			<1	>16	0.20	2.03
Incr. Superf.									2.25					2.25	2.25	
Barra							0.7									
S. Rocchino surface												>160				
Highest values	4.2	0.19	0.10		0.20	0.20	>1.6	4.81	1.70	>16	>16	>16	6.9			

microcystin was 218.9 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, with a peak of 1,092 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, and the TDI could be reached after the ingestion of only 2.56 g. The microcystin concentration of a homogenated extract of three full *P. clarkii* was 120 $\mu\text{g Kg}^{-1}$, and the TDI corresponded to the ingestion of 25 g of specimen.

In the other species, the TDI was reached after a daily intake of flesh > 1 kg and the risk of toxic effects for the consumer is very low.

Based on these results, fishing of *Mugil cephalus* and of *Procambarus clarkii* as well as sport fishing have been forbidden in Lake Massaciuccoli and in the wetland; recreational activities have also been prohibited in the periods and in the areas where the presence of scums

was observed.

Acknowledgments

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PICES Working Group HAB, Honolulu

At the PICES Annual Meeting in Honolulu, Hawaii from 15-23 October, the a joint PICES-IOC workshop on 'Developing a North Pacific HAB data resource-II' will be held with Hak-Gyoon Kim (Co-Chair), and Vera Trainer (Co-Chair) and Henrik Enevoldsen (IOC) as conveners. At last year's joint PICES/IOC Workshop

on "Harmful algal blooms – Harmonization of data", representatives from PICES member countries accepted an offer from IOC/ICES to utilize their successful harmful algal event meta-database (HAE-DAT) format on a trial basis. The goal of the 2004 workshop is to provide an interim "report card" on the use of this database. The cen-

tral tasks are to ascertain how well the database process worked and to identify any difficulties in data delivery from member nations.

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• Mexico

Marine die-offs from *Chattonella marina* and *Ch. cf. ovata* in Kun Kaak Bay, Sonora in the Gulf of California

In Kun Kaak Bay, Sonora, Mexico, fishermen observed extensive fish mortality during early April 2003. They also observed large numbers of dead pen shells, clams, octopus, and sea cucumbers in the bottom layers and sea floor. These observations were concurrent with reports of green-yellow discoloration at the surface. During May, underwater surveys were carried out and samples were taken to assess phytoplankton and nutrients where surface discolorations were densest (Fig. 1). Abiotic data were obtained for temperature using a bucket thermometer (precision $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$), salinity with a hand-held refractometer (precision ± 1 psu), and nutrients using a commercial kit (HACH) [1]. Surface samples taken with a bottle were fixed (1 ml Lugol's acetate in 100 ml sample) for plankton observations. Samples of 10 ml were allowed to settle for 24 hours and observed with a phase contrast inverted microscope adapted with a Whipple disc (1 mm² divided in 100- μm squares). Photomicrographs were obtained using an inverted phase contrast microscope at 200X.

Results

Underwater observations detected a thick viscous layer on the bottom, sometimes forming balls. Fish and mollusks were in an advanced stage of putrefaction, precluding its use for detecting toxins. Estimated area covered by this event was 95 km² (Fig.1). This area is recognized as a natural reservoir of *Aterina tuberculosa* (pen shell) and *Callinectes sp.* (blue crab), where stocks were very abundant. Both fisheries were severely damaged. Currently, very few individuals of these two species are found, severely affecting the livelihood of more than 60 diver-fishermen. Global Greengrants Fund is currently assessing the damage suffered on the different fishing banks. Stranded fish collected at the local beaches were used to study affected species (Table 1). It was not possible to assess the volume of stranded fish because local authorities remo-

Fig. 1. Map of the Kun Kaak Bay area, showing location of the sampling stations and extent of the red tide.

ved the dead fish daily. Fishermen observed that fish were carried southward by local currents to distant beaches. In the region most severely affected, laboratories raising post-larvae shrimp were in operation. They reported bad odours coming from the water and up to 40% loss in post-larvae. Mortality level was controlled by increasing ozonization of the intake water.

Quantitative plankton analyses, based on shape and size [3], indicate a strong dominance by *Chattonella marina* (Fig.2). Those with size $>70 \mu\text{m}$ may represent *Chattonella*

cf. ovata (9%) (Fig. 2a). Abundance reached 480 to 568 cells ml⁻¹ at coastal sampling stations, 324 cells ml⁻¹ one km off shore, and 142 cells ml⁻¹ on the sea bottom (Table 2). Even though many ce-

Table 1. List of species stranded in high numbers during the HAB in April, 2003

FISH	
Common name	Scientific name
Burrito	<i>Haemulopsis nitidus</i>
Tieso del Pacifico???	<i>Ophichthus triserialis</i>
-----	<i>Congriperla estriada</i>
-----	<i>Ophiodon galaeoides</i>
Jawfish	<i>Gnathypops snyderi</i>
Lenguado tapadera (flatfish)	<i>Citarichthys gilberti</i>
BENTHOS	
Callos de hacha (penshells)	<i>Atrina maura</i>
	<i>Atrina tuberculosa</i>
	<i>Pinna rugosa</i>
Almeja reina (clam)	<i>Dosinia ponderosa</i>
	<i>Megapitaria aurantiaca</i> and <i>Megapitaria squalida</i>
Almeja chocolata (clam)	<i>Chione gnidia</i>
Almeja china (clam)	<i>Hexaplex erythrotomus</i>
Caracol rosa espinoso (conch)	<i>Laevycardium elatum</i>
Almeja amarilla, botijona, o hiluda (clams)	
Pulpos de diferentes especies (octopi of several species)	

Fig. 2. (a) Vegetative cell of *Chattonella marina*; (b) Vegetative cell of *Chattonella cf. ovata*; (c) Small cells of *Ch. Marina*; (d) Cyst or sphaeric non-motile cell. Scale bars = 30 μ . Cells fixed with acid Lugol.

Table 2. Phytoplankton abundance (cells ml^{-1}) in Kun Kaak Bay, Sonora, Mexico on 17 May 2003

Raphidophyceae	E-1	%	E-2	%	E-2 f	%	E-3	%	E-4	%	E-5	%
<i>Chattonella marina</i>	568	25.53	324	51.8	142	24.7	518	57.9	555	53.8	480	35.5
Dinophyceae	691	31	232	37.1	36	6.31	187	20.9	311	30.2	128	9.48
Bacillariophyceae	952	42.7	58	9.28	388	67.4	173	19.3	129	12.5	728	53.8
Euglenophyceae	4	0.17	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0.55	0	0
Dictyochophyceae	13	0.6	11	1.76	10	1.67	17	1.9	19	1.86	17	1.27
Cyanophyceae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	1.12	0	0
Total	2229	100	625	100	576	100	895	100	1031	100	1353	100

Table 3. Nutrients (mg l^{-1}) in samples from Kun Kaak Bay.

Sampling Place	17 May 2003		22 May 2003	
	NO ₃	PO ₄	NO ₃	PO ₄
E1	0.2	1.09	1.5	0.29
E2	0.1	1.09		
E2F	0.0	0.72		
E3	0.1	0.54		
E4	?	?		
E5	0.1	>3.0	1.4	0.3
Canal Entrance			1.8	0.26

ells were deformed, the cells were easily distinguished and measured: (n = 43); length 30-80 μ m ($\frac{1}{2}$ 49.7) and width 15-47 μ m ($\frac{1}{2}$ 29.7). Mean length was slightly less than the reports of Band Schmidt *et al.* [4] (a difference of 12 to 27 μ m). According to Imai *et al.* [5] *Ch. marina* (Fig. 2b) may be present in a range of sizes, as reported here. *Ch. marina* cells >50 μ m represented 35% (Figs. 2 a and b) and cells <50 μ m amounted to 65% (Fig. 2c). Some cysts were observed as well as circular non-motile cells [4] (Fig. 2d). We observed all cell cycle stages reported by Imai *et al.* [5] including pre-encystment, haploid and diploid small cells, and vegetative G1 and G2 phase cells. These data support the idea that this was not an

uncommon event and that this species is well adapted to local conditions. This species was recently reported in Mexican waters [4], but it was not recorded as forming blooms and contributing to fish and shellfish mortality. The causes for this HAB may be related to physical conditions that prevailed at this time. Available data indicate that SST was optimal 25.9-26.9°C (25°C [5]), but salinity (36-38 psu) was well above the reported optimum (20 psu [5]). A high concentration of phosphate was depleted over the following few days (Table 3). The sources of phosphate are natural seasonal upwelling and surplus

there is a serious risk to aquaculture and fishing in the region from noxious and toxic blooms, as shown here. This event should be considered a warning: blooms may increase and become periodic, in turn disrupting primary economic activities and impacting human and marine animal health. This event also calls for development and support of permanent monitoring activities and research that may provide information for better management of HABs, including mitigation.

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outflow from aquaculture enterprises in the area (larvae-producing laboratories and extensive shrimp farms). The phosphate allows blooms to last longer, hence severely affecting marine biota and the marine environment, in general. Nevertheless, available data does not help us determine the contribution of each source, but common sense suggests a few ways to control anthropogenic inputs to the environment. This includes construction of retention dams and natural filters to reduce organic matter and excess nutrient by-products of aquaculture.

Consequences

Kun Kaak Bay has been recognized as a zone of high productivity for some time [6]. It is under the influence of upwelling currents and is well known for high primary productivity of diatoms, of which, *Stephanopyxis palmeriana* is distinctive [7]. Recently, dominance has shifted to dinoflagellates and raphidophytes, a well known indicator of eutrophication. Consequently,

(Cont'd from p. 1)

the establishment of mechanisms for dissemination and exchange of red tide related information among scientists and technicians in organizations responsible for the monitoring in Asia and the neighboring countries.

To seek a suitable approach to be use of remote sensing for red tide monitoring, the first Workshop on «Red Tide Monitoring in the Asian Coastal Waters» was held at the University of Tokyo in Tokyo, Japan, on 10-12 March, 2003 as a part of the «Red Tide Watcher» project. This workshop provided a forum for both red tide biologists and the remote sensing community to exchange information for enhancing mutual understanding of the problem, and to share common ideas on key issues. The organizers sincerely intended this workshop would be the first step towards establishing a red tide surveillance system in Asia.

The workshop was attended by more than 75 participants from 13 countries representing Japan, Korea, China, Hong Kong, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Indonesia, Spain, New Zealand and the USA. Thirty papers were presented covering eight sessions/groups, viz, 1) Introduction, 2) Korean Waters, 3) China Sea, 4) Japanese Waters, 5) Thailand and Philippines Waters, 6) Vietnam, Malaysia and Indonesia Waters, 7) Other Areas, 8) General discussion.

The workshop was fruitful in establishing mutual understanding between remote sensing oceanographers and red tide biologists. A summary of the outcome of this workshop was as follows: 1) Ocean color remote sensing techniques have proven to be a useful tool to detect meso-scale discolorations caused by high-biomass microalgal proliferations (various terms were suggested, such as algal bloom, phytoplankton proliferations, meso-scale discoloration), 2) It was realized that ocean color as well as other remote sensing data (chlorophyll, sea surface temperature, wind etc.) is useful to understand the processes for development and decay of red tides, 3) An understanding of oceanographic processes will allow us to analyze how to use remote sensing data for red tide research and monitoring, 4) Accumula-

tion of knowledge on red tide occurrence was confirmed in various regions, 5) It was strongly felt that cooperation between biologists, satellite experts, oceanographers, and meteorologists is essential. Mutual communication and understanding among the disciplines is a pre-requisite, 6) Species level information is essential for red tide monitoring, 7) An optical approach is promising in identifying responsible functional groups of organisms, 8) In order to derive red tide information from remote sensing data, optical research on species-specific characteristics should be enhanced, 9) Specification of *in situ* database should be redefined to fit interpretation of satellite derived data, 10) Development of algorithms for optically complex water masses should be promoted. 11) The combined use of *in situ* mooring instruments is recommended, 12) Future real-time monitoring system of red tide should be discussed on the basis of scientific and technological researches using *in situ* and remote sensing methods.

After the workshop, several activities of the project followed. These included: 1) A small symposium for the standardization of species identification was held in Nagasaki, Japan, on 21-27 September, 2003, to list important red tide species/genera that cause taxonomic problems, to identify the quality of the problem in each species/genus, and to establish strategies to solve the identified problem. 2) The first Korea-Japan Workshop on Ocean Color (KJWOC) was held in Nagasaki, Japan, on 10-12 January, 2003. The 1st KJWOC was attended by more than 30 participants. Twenty-two papers were presented covering seven sessions, viz, 1. Opening, 2. Satellite Systems, 3. Atmospheric Correction and In-Water Algorithms, 4. Red Tide, 5. North Pacific Ecosystems, 6. North Pacific and Other Ecosystems, 7. General discussion and Closing. The 1st KJWOC was fruitful and a good first step for collaboration between Korea and Japan. 3) A multi-disciplinary survey on a whole-bay scale red tide was conducted in Manila Bay from March 19 to 23, 2004. The survey aimed to understand bio-optical properties and physiological ecology of green *Noctiluca* (*Noctiluca scintillans*

with the endosymbiont *Pedinomonas noctilucae*). Subjects examined during the cruise include spatial distribution of phytoplankton, growth, grazing, photosynthesis and respiration of *N. scintillans*, and bio-optical properties of the *Noctiluca* bloom.

Cooperation among satellite oceanographer and red tide biologists, coupled with efficient use of *in situ* and remote sensing techniques, would strengthen the future real-time monitoring system of red tide.

For further information, please visit our website: <http://fol.fs.a.u-tokyo.ac.jp/rtw/>

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HANA Network: Harmful Algae of North Africa

At the «Regional Training Course on Harmful Algae» organised by IOC of UNESCO in cooperation with the AECI, NAUTA, IEO, COPEMED and DANIDA, from 1 to 12 December 2003 at the INSTM, Salammbô/La Goulette, Tunisia. Following the initiative of Prof. Y. Halim, the participants established a network for Harmful Algae of North Africa «HANA».

The HANA network was conceived with two general objectives in mind: to promote organized research and monitoring in the region and to establish a link between the HANA region and the international programmes on HABs.

The HANA region (Mauritania, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya and Egypt) has considerable marine resources consisting among others of fish and shellfish mariculture and tourism. Economic losses due to harmful blooms are caused by the proliferation of a variety of species belonging to Bacillariophyceae, Cyanophyceae, Dinophyceae, Cryptophyceae and Prasinophyceae. In this region more than elsewhere knowledge about the processes driving the incidence of such blooms is far from satisfactory. Reports on HABs are scattered and often result from unassisted individual efforts. HANA will encourage the exchange of information with the aim of creating a continuously updated data and metadata-base. Three types of information will be collected, archived and made available:

- 1) The incidence of HABs, the species involved and the concomitant environmental conditions
- 2) The personnel involved, their areas of specialization and their levels of expertise

Participants and teachers of the IOC Regional Training Course on Harmful Algae.

- 3) The relevant regional publications.

With the assistance of IOC, HANA will work towards further enhancing research capabilities in the region. Advanced training workshops will be organized and a digital identification guide to harmful species of the region will be developed. Working groups will bring together scientists and managers for exchange of information and experience and for updating their knowledge. Some selected scientists will be given the opportunity to interact with the international scientific community by attending relevant meetings and conferences, as happened with the Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics in Corsica, from 5 to 8 April 2004.

Some steps have already been taken to collect the above information:

- The regional publications
- An inventory of the researchers of the region.

Progress towards the implementation of HANA objectives can only be achieved through intra-regional cooperation in one or more Pilot Projects supported by IOC.

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South America HAB Internet Portal

IOC-UNESCO is for 2004-2005 funding the development of an internet portal on HAB for South America. The project will be implemented by the South American IOC Working Group on HAB (COI FANSA). The portal will include a web based learning component. The project will be initiated at a workshop in Itajai, Brazil, 4-6 June

2004. Contact: Chair COI FANSA, Dr. Leonardo Guzmán, lguzman@ifop.cl

IOC Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB)

The IPHAB is scheduling its next session for March 2005. The IPHAB is established to set priorities of international HAB issues and activities. You can find the IPHAB Terms of Reference,

List of Members, and IPHAB reports at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/act2.htm>

For more information: Chair IPHAB, Dr. Beatriz Reguera, Instituto Español de Oceanografía, Centro Oceanográfico de Vigo, Aptdo. 1552, 36280 Vigo, Spain. Tel: 34 986 49 21 11, Fax: 34 986 49 23 51, E-mail: beatriz.reguera@vi.ieo.es

GEOHAB

Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms

OPEN SCIENCE MEETING: HABs IN UPWELLING SYSTEMS

The Global Ecology and Oceanography of Harmful Algal Blooms (GEOHAB) programme was initiated in 1999 by the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO to develop a research program on the ecological and oceanographic mechanisms underlying the population dynamics of harmful algal blooms (HABs). The end goal of this research is to allow the development of observation systems and models that will enable prediction of HABs, thereby reducing their impacts on the health of humans and marine organisms, as well as their economic and social impacts on societies.

The GEOHAB *Implementation Plan* (GEOHAB, 2003) specifies the formation of Core Research Projects (CRPs) related to four ecosystem types—upwelling systems, fjords and coastal embayments, eutrophic systems, and stratified systems. These CRPs are to be initiated through small, focused open science meetings. The first of these open science meetings was hosted at the Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e das Pescas (INIAP-IPIMAR), in Lisbon, Portugal from 17-20 November 2003, and focused on HABs in upwelling systems. The meeting served to identify interested participants and research regions and to bring together the international community to design core research. Meeting participants discussed a wide variety of research topics related to HABs in upwelling systems, which the meeting planning committee [co-chaired by Grant Pitcher – South Africa and Teresa Moita – Portugal, and

including Francisco Figueiras – Spain, Raphael Kudela – USA, Trevor Probyn – South Africa, and Vera Trainer – USA] distilled into 8 high priority research activities:

1 An ecologically based classification of the different harmful species based on their adaptation to the multiple sub-habitats characteristic of upwelling ecosystems. Included in this classification of HAB species in upwelling systems will be the functional role of morphological, physiological, behavioural and life-history characteristics, at the cellular level.

2 Identification of the seed strategies employed by HAB species within upwelling systems. Establishment of the sites of HAB initiation and characterisation of environmental influences on the life history stages of HAB species in upwelling systems is considered a priority in developing a predictive capability.

3 Determination of the influence of small-scale physical processes on the growth and dispersion of HAB species. Turbulent mixing determines much high-frequency environmental fluctuation and in so doing can control nutrient, irradiance, and phytoplankton patchiness, and is also known to affect plankton growth rates. Varying responses in terms of the succession of species within and among upwelling systems will allow inferences of the properties of the upper water column regulating species succession and the development of HABs.

4 An investigation of the nutritional physiology of target species

as related to the natural variation in nutrient signals. Although time series, field measurements of nutrient concentrations can provide valuable insight to nutrient dynamics, provided that trans-boundary fluxes are quantified, direct measurements of regeneration and assimilation rates need also to be performed using isotope tracer methodology. These measurements will serve to provide meaningful input to biogeochemical models that can be employed in a predictive manner when coupled with the primary hydrodynamic forcing typical of upwelling ecosystems.

5 An assessment of genetic predisposition versus environmental conditions in the toxin production of target species in different upwelling systems. Variability in toxin production is likely caused by a combination of genotype and environmental conditions and elucidation of these respective roles in toxigenicity is critical in developing a predictive capability. Differences in the absolute toxicity of a given species in separate upwelling regions may be exploited to allow characterization of genes important in toxin synthesis.

6 Determination of the importance of coastal morphology and bathymetry on the dynamics of HABs in upwelling systems. These influences are responsible for creating alternating patterns of active and passive upwelling circulations along the coast which may serve in creating sites favouring bloom initiation, retention, dispersion, etc. Characterisation of these sites will assist in understanding their role in the dynamics of HABs.

7 Field based observations incor-

The GEOHAB Open Science Meeting on HABs in Upwelling Systems was hosted by the National Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (INIA-IPIMAR), Lisbon Portugal.

porating measurements of cross-shelf and along-shore advection and their role in the initiation, transport, accumulation and dispersion of HABs. These observations should be made with reference to both vegetative and resting stages of HAB species.

8 Identification of climate indicators as predictors of HAB events in upwelling systems. Evidence exists to suggest that variations in upwelling intensities and locations, and also ecosystems have occurred in concert with warming of the earth's climate. Research is required to relate the effects of climate change, and associated variation in the predominant physical and chemical forcing mechanisms, on HAB species and communities that typify coastal upwelling environments.

Our understanding of and ability to predict HABs in upwelling systems over the next 5-10 years will reflect the extent to which the GEOHAB CRP can answer these questions. The CRP – HABs in Upwelling Systems is built on the premise that understanding the ecology and oceanography of HABs in upwelling systems will benefit from a comparative approach, which is the method of choice when controlled experimentation is not practical. To the extent that experimental control in the study of marine ecosystems is problematic, comparison presents a potentially powerful alternative for drawing scientific inference. Comparisons with respect to HABs will incorporate the grouping of species from upwelling systems. Assessment of the extent to which these HAB species respond in a similar way within these systems will

allow the oceanographic processes that influence HAB population dynamics and community interactions to be established. Equally important will be identification of upwelling systems that have dissimilar HAB species or groupings. In addition, understanding the response of harmful algae to perturbations within upwelling systems will assist in prediction, and identification of divergences from predicted responses will also be informative.

The GEOHAB Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) will help provide international coordination for the CRP – HABs in Upwelling Systems, through the establishment of a GEOHAB CRP Subcommittee. This Subcommittee will commit to the promotion of comparative research and the involvement of individuals from the Californian, Iberian and Benguela upwelling regions, and from other major upwelling systems. The subcommittee will be responsible for working with scientists involved in the CRP to ensure that they coordinate their research, using the same measurement protocols, sharing data, and contributing to observation and model development. One or two members of the CRP Subcommittee will be members of the international GEOHAB SSC, to ensure a strong linkage between the Subcommittee and the SSC.

Reference

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More detail at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/GEOHAB.htm> and <http://www.jhu.edu/scor/GEOHAB.htm> and <http://ioc.unesco.org/geohabcore/>

Working Group on HAB Dynamics

The ICES-IOC Working Group on Harmful Algal Bloom Dynamics met at Corsica, 5-8 March. The tasks for 2004 included the review of existing phytoplankton population dynamics models with particular emphasis on prediction of HAB events, and the review of biological loss processes of selected HAB species. The WG also discussed environmental dynamics and impacts of individual phycotoxins and their metabolites enabled by new analytical technologies. The WG reviewed plans for a planned (2005) Workshop on New and Classic Techniques for the Determination of Numerical Abundance of HAB-species. Every year the WG collate and assess national harmful algal event reports and update the decadal mapping of harmful algal events for the IOC-ICES harmful algal event database, HAE-DAT. Progress was reported in the computerized production of decadal maps from country reports, including the revision of reports already in the database covering the last 10 years. A special task this year was to start preparations to summarize the distribution and number of harmful algal blooms in the North Sea for the period 2000-2004, and any trends over recent decades in the occurrence of these blooms for input to the ICES Regional Ecosystem Study Group for the North Sea in 2006. More detail at <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/act6.htm>

The meeting was hosted by University of Liege (Belgium) at their marine field station STARESO in Corsica (France).

The 11th International Conference on Harmful Algae will be held under the auspices of the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA) and the Phycological Society of Southern Africa (PSSA). The Conference will provide a broad forum for phycologists, microbiologists, toxicologists, physiologists, molecular biologists, aquatic ecologists and managers to address and exchange research findings and perspectives concerning all aspects of toxic and harmful algae. The

venue for the Conference will be the Cape Town International Convention Centre on the Foreshore of the Cape Town Business District, South Africa.

Important Dates:

Final Date for Receipt of Abstracts

31 May 2004

Early Registration Deadline

15 August 2004

Late Registration Deadline

15 October 2004

Website: www.botany.uwc.ac.za/pssa

Conference Secretariat:

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HAB-DIR: International Directory of Experts in Harmful Algae and Their Effects on Fisheries and Public Health

This international directory lists research scientists, fisheries managers, public health officials, aquaculture professionals, physicians, and animal health specialists who are experienced in dealing with toxic and harmful algal event and their impact on fisheries and public health. The directory is intended to improve and accelerate international information exchange and rapid access to experts who can respond quickly to these outbreaks and thus help reduce the consequences to fisheries and public health.

The first edition of this directory was published in 1990 by Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution Sea Grant program. The second edition was a co-operative effort by the U.S. Department of Commerce, U.S. NOAA National Marine Fisheries Service, U.S. Northeast Fisheries Science Center, and the Harmful Algal Bloom Programme of the IOC. The Directory is today an inter-

net based product prepared by the IOC Science and Communication Centre on Harmful Algae, Copenhagen.

The Directory can be updated and amended on-line. Are you already in the Directory? Maybe your data needs to be updated?

<http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/data.htm>

PUBLICATIONS

The following publications can be ordered from <http://ioc.unesco.org/hab/pub.htm>:

Manual on Harmful Marine Microalgae, Hallegraeff, G. M. et al (Eds) UNESCO Monographs on Oceanographic Methodology, UNESCO 2003.

Villaba, A., Reguera, B., Romalde J., Bieras, L.R. (Eds) 2003. Molluscan Shellfish Safety, Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Molluscan Shellfish Safety. Xunta de Galicia and Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, Vigo and Paris. 620 pp.

Microalgues potentiellement

nuisibles de l'océan Indien Occidental - Guide basé sur une étude préliminaire / Potentially Harmful Microalgae of the Western Indian Ocean - a guide based on a preliminary survey, IOC Technical Series No. 41.

"Floraciones Algaes Nocivas en el Cono Sur Americano" by E.A. Sar, M.E. Ferrario & B. Reguera. Instituto Español de Oceanografía, 2002, 312 pp. (ISBN: 84-95877-01-5; NIPO: 406-02-001-9). (Spanish only)

Monitoring and Management Strategies for Harmful Algal Blooms in Coastal Waters, by D. M. Anderson, P. Andersen, V. M. Bricelj, J. J. Cullen, and J. E. Rensel. APEC Report # 201-MR-01.1, Asia Pacific Economic Programme, and Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, Technical Series No. 59, Paris, France, 2001.

Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Harmful Algal Blooms, Hobart, Australia, 7-11 February 2000, Hallegraeff, G.M., et al. (Eds). IOC of UNESCO, 2001.

ISSHA

International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

<http://www.issha.org/>

ISSHA President's Corner

April 1-3, 2004 was an historic time for the International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae (ISSHA). It was the first meeting of the Council which consists of the President, two Vice-Presidents, Secretary, Treasurer (the Executive) and 9 of the 14 recently elected Council members from all over the world. Council members represent Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) disciplines from Denmark, Norway, Sweden, England, Germany, Spain, Italy, Canada, United States, Japan, South Korea, and Australia. The meeting was held in Hornbaek, Denmark, a short distance from Copenhagen, in a rural, beautiful and quiet setting.

The goals of this first Council meeting were to review the objectives of ISSHA, highlight the benefits of ISSHA membership, and determine how ISSHA could affiliate with existing initiatives in the field of harmful algae without competing with those initiatives. Committees on Elections, Membership, Travel Awards, Achievement Awards, Finance, Conference Programs, and Publications were established and goals set. An additional Ad Hoc Committee on Special Projects was established to handle requests for participation in different activities such as HAB maps, expert panels, and support for training programs. Each committee has assignments with deliverables to help achieve Society objectives.

Some examples of assignments: funds will be solicited to support stu-

dent travel to HAB conferences, including the 11th HAB2004 in South Africa; the ISSHA website will be modified to present more information to members; ISSHA will sponsor HAB conferences, in collaboration with local organizing committees, starting with the 12th conference in Copenhagen; ISSHA members will edit HAB conference proceedings and IOC will publish the proceedings. ISSHA will also consider producing special publications as warranted. Another merger of initiatives is in this Harmful Algae News issue. A section on ISSHA activities will appear in each HAN issue. Just as importantly, ISSHA Council members and other members have pledged to increase the contributions to HAN on a regular basis.

Please go to the ISSHA website at www.issha.org for the posting of the minutes from the recent Council meeting, including a listing of the benefits of ISSHA membership.

First came the Statutes that helped provide the framework for our Society and then this Council meeting gave us the momentum to move on. I would like to personally thank the Executive and Council for their dedication and belief in this young, growing Society of several hundred members. If you are not a member, please join. If you have not renewed, please renew. The membership form is contained in this issue. At 20 USD a year for a membership fee, it is one of the best values around.

See you in Cape Town.

Karen Steidinger, President of ISSHA

The ISSHA Council quorum 2004

ISSHA AWARDS: CALL FOR NOMINATIONS

Current members of ISSHA are invited to submit nominations for the following awards:

The Yasumoto Lifetime Achievement Award

This award is offered in recognition of a long, and outstanding record of contribution to harmful algal research. Previous recipients: Dr. F.J.R. (Max) Taylor (2000), Dr. G.R. Hasle (2002), and Dr. T. Smayda (2002). Other senior scientists similarly honored by the harmful algal research community before ISSHA included Dr. L. Provasoli and Dr. E. Balech.

The Young Scientist Achievement Award

This award is offered in recognition of outstanding achievement in any

aspect of harmful algal research by a scientist early in their career (i.e. within ten years of receiving their PhD). The award is intended for an exceptional or "break-through" contribution to an area of harmful algae research, rather than a cumulative record of achievement. Previous recipient: Dr. C. Scholin (2002).

Any ISSHA member may submit nominations for either achievement award, which should provide a complete, yet succinct description of the nominee's contribution (not more than one page). Nominations should be sent by e-mail to Barrie Dale (barrie.dale@geo.uio.no), Chair of the Committee on Achievement Awards, to be received no later than 1 September 2004. It should be noted that ISSHA does not necessarily give achievement awards at every International HAB Conference.

Nominations received by 1 September 2004, will be considered by the ISSHA Council, and eventual awards will be presented at the 11th HAB Conference in Cape Town, South Africa, November 2004.

The Maureen Keller Student Presentation Awards

These awards will be presented for the best oral and poster presentations at the 11th HAB Conference. A student is considered eligible for these awards for a period of up to one year following a successful defense of their thesis. A tribute to Maureen Keller may be seen at the following link: <http://www.bigelow.org/mk.html>.

Travel Awards

A committee has been formed to coordinate efforts to raise and distribute funds for travel to international HAB conferences. The committee is chaired by Don Anderson, with assistance from members of the ISSHA Council (Allan Cembella, Henrik Enevoldsen, Karen Steidinger, Yasuwo Fukuyo, and Beatriz Reguera), as well as other ISSHA members, to be named later. Assistance from additional members of the HAB community is welcome – please contact the chair (danderson@whoi.edu) with suggestions or if you wish to volunteer your services. Of particular interest are suggestions of sources of funds that could be contacted by the Committee.

Travel awards are anticipated for students, postdocs, and researchers, the latter generally being from developing countries. Among the criteria for selection will be the following:

- Membership in ISSHA
- Availability of "matching" funds
- Economic status of country of origin
- Prior travel awards to the same candidate
- Commitment to an oral or a poster presentation

Nominations sought for ISSHA Executive

The International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae is seeking nominations for the ISSHA Executive (President, two Vice-Presidents, Secretary and Treasurer). The current Executive (Steidinger, Cembella, Oshima, Bates, and Enevoldsen, respectively) are not eligible for the same offices they currently hold although they are eligible for other offices. Those nominated must be current ISSHA members. Following the nominations, the Elections Committee will prepare a ballot for mailout to ISSHA members on 01 August 2004. The ballots will be counted during the 11th International Conference on Harmful Algae (15-19 November 2004), when the new Executive will take effect.

Please submit your nominations by 01 JULY 2004 to Dr. Stephen S. Bates at bates@dfm-mpo.gc.ca or Fisheries and Oceans Canada, Gulf Fisheries Centre, 343 Université Ave., Moncton NB E1C 9B6, Canada.

President:

Vice-President:

Vice-President:

Secretary:

Treasurer:

Application for Membership: International Society for the Study of Harmful Algae

Name: _____

Address: _____

E-mail: _____

Tel: _____

Type of Membership (\$US or equivalent Euros):

Regular (\$20) Student (\$10) Corporate (\$40)

Credit Card:

Visa: MasterCard: Eurocard: Maestro: Visa-Electron:

Card number: _____

Expiry date: _____ / _____ (MUST be indicated)

Security code: _____ (last three digits on back of credit card)

Amount USD: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

This form is approved by PBS. VAT (or SE #): SE 21 41 61 42

If you prefer to pay by bank transfer please transfer via your bank or by home banking (e-banking) to the account of ISSHA: Nordea Bank, IBAN DK7920008473580633, Frederiksborggade 14-16, 1360 Copenhagen K, Denmark.

Checks are not accepted.

Send or fax this form to:

Henrik Enevoldsen, ISSHA Treasurer

University of Copenhagen

Øster Farimagsgade 2D

DK-1353 Copenhagen K

DENMARK

Fax: (45) 33134447

HARMFUL ALGAE NEWS

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